

THE EFFECT OF THE MEDICINAL PLANT FERULA SUMBOL ON THE ANIMAL ORGANISM

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Annotation: The article devoted to open the theme” the effect of the medicinal plant Ferula sumbol on the animal organism. Moreover, in the article medicinal properties and culinary usage of this plant were noted.

Key words: chemotypes, “gum ammoniac of Morocco”, brevifolia, finest-grade, finest-grade.

Ferula communis, the giant fennel, is a species of flowering plant in the carrot family Apiaceae. It is related to the common fennel (Foeniculum vulgare), which belongs to the same family. Ferula communis is a tall herbaceous perennial plant. It is found in Mediterranean and East African woodlands and shrublands. It was known in antiquity as laser or narthex. Its young stems and inflorescences were eaten in ancient Rome, and are still eaten in Morocco today. However, culinary uses of this species are not always safe and poisoning may occur. In Sardinia two different chemotypes of Ferula communis have been identified: poisonous (especially to animals like sheep, goats, cattle, and horses) and non-poisonous. They differ in both secondary metabolites patterning and enzymatic composition. The resin of the subspecies F. communis subsp. brevifolia is called “gum ammoniac of Morocco”. The phenolic compound ferulic acid is named for the giant fennel, from which it can be isolated. In Ancient Greek mythology, Prometheus gave mortals fire by hiding it

in the plant's hollow stalk.

Since antiquity, the resin of *Ferula* species has been used for medicinal purposes. The resin, in the form of a sticky latex, was usually extracted from the lower stalk or root, with the root resin being the finest-grade. Where the resin of giant fennel (*Ferula communis*) was farmed, a small hole was pierced in its root with a sharp instrument, after clearing away all rocks and earth that cling to the exposed root. A small trench was dug beneath the root and overlaid with several smooth and flat stones at the bottom for collecting the exuded resin. The piercing was made deep enough into the root or lower stalk to ensure a steady flow of resin on its own pressure[1].The resin was usually harvested in the dry and hot summer months, when dampness and moisture could not corrupt the resin. The resin hardens when exposed to the air, upon which it changes color to a brownish-red. The resin that exudes in coagulated, drop-like form is considered superior to that which runs down loosely.

Ferula communis or giant fennel: giant is not an exaggeration since this spectacular architectural plant is known to grow to 3 metres. The lower leaves are 3 to 4 pinnates, finest-grade. soft, glabrous, green on both sides and usually have a conspicuous sheathing base. The lamina is finely divided into linear and filiform lobes. The latter have no distinct revolute margin and are up to 50 mm. long, but no more than 1 mm. wide. The upper fertile leaves of the inflorescence are progressively reduced to a conspicuous sheathing base. The bracts are absent and the bracteoles are few or absent. The stem is very robust, wide (3-7 cm. in diameter), full, finely striated and can grow to 2 to 3 metres high. The terminal fertile umbel is large and composed of 20 to 40 rays. The flower is bright yellow[2]. The fruit (mericarp) is elliptical or oblong-elliptical, strongly compressed dorsally; the length is varied between 7 and 15 mm. *Ferula communis* has a well-developed, strong root system. Slight differences exist between the two varieties reported in Morocco. The leaves of the *brevifolia* variety are light green and markedly smaller than the leaf-lobes of the *genuina* variety. It flowers from

May to July.

Ferula communis grows in forest glades and in the pasture of plains and mountains up to an altitude of 2 200 m. It has an enormous root system and is drought-resistant. The perennial seeds germinate very irregularly over a long period. Temperatures of less than +5°C are very effective. Seed trays should not be discarded prematurely. Constant moisture must be maintained. Do not leave in direct sunlight. Germination to transplanting takes 4 to 8 weeks. Reproduction is by root and seeds. *Ferula communis* L. is a source of resin gum, obtained by incision of the root, and used in traditional medicine for a variety of ailments. It was also reported to be toxic in man and especially in livestock. The fessoukh or the resin gum of *Ferula communis* is a specifically Moroccan product, known in Arabic countries and up to India under this name. Moroccan fessoukh is appreciated for certain uses in countries where *Ferula communis* apparently grows. The demand for the fessoukh is the main cause of the intense exploitation of the plant. In addition the pre-blossom inflorescences of *Ferula communis* have culinary uses.

In Morocco, only *Ferula communis* L. var. *genuina* is used to extract the resin gum. For this, the leaves are cut down at ground level, and then the top of the root is sliced off. The latex secretion oozes out and is collected every 7 to 10 days, several times. Each time, the upper part of the root is cut again. The collection is done in summer on hot days since it seems that hot weather increases the secretion of the latex[3]. The latex that is milky and white at the beginning becomes progressively solid and may turn brown with time. In Morocco, the uses of fessoukh are about the same every where. Mixed with olive oil, it is recommended by practitioners for external use for a variety of skin diseases. In friction it is used against moths or ringworm, rheumatism, and to heal in the feet cracks. Gum resin is also added to some depilatory preparations. Orally it is prescribed by practitioners as an antihelmintic, diuretic, vermifuge, and analgesic, and for pains in the joints, female sterility, and rheumatism, as well as as an

emetic. The roasted flower buds are absorbed as a vermifuge, an anti-hysterical, for dysentery, and as an aphrodisiac. The whole plant is said to possess antispasmodic properties. Fessoukh seems to be famous because of its use in magic and sorcery. Fessoukh means that “which undoes spells (magical)”. Fessoukh is frequently used in ritual or magic fumigation and in sorcery and counter-sorcery. Fumigation is believed to ward off the “evil spirits” and the “evil”. The roots are also used, especially in a preparation used for hair care. It is used for skin diseases, rheumatism, cracks in the feet, helminthic disease, pains in the joints, female sterility, rheumatism, hysteria, and dysentery. It is antispasmodic, vermifugal, aphrodisiac, and can be used against moths or ringworm, as a depilatory, an emetic, a diuretic and an analgesic.

Consumption of the plant is not recent but goes back to classical times. In Roman times, Pliny noted that the stems of the plant were consumed and much appreciated. It was also reported that even the “cotes” of the leaves were consumed in North Africa during periods of food shortage. In Morocco, nowadays, the young stems or prebossom inflorescence called l'boubal are sold in the medina as a legume[4]. Some delicious dishes are prepared from it. The most common way of preparation is to cook the unopened inflorescence with steam like couscous and add olive oil, vinegar, and other spices as desired. The young stems are also eaten as fresh vegetables, but this is a new practice, seen in modern and European families. The consumption of the plant is not totally harmless; several reports stress the toxicity of such use.

To sum up all information, it should be noted that Coumarins and daucane sesquiterpenes were identified in solvent extracts of the different parts of *Ferula communis*. The chemical composition of the essential oil was also investigated. The most important characteristic of *Ferula communis* is its capacity to synthesize 4-hydroxycoumarins. At this time, no other plant is known to be able to do so. Among these compounds are: ferulenol, 20-hydroxyferulenol, omega-hydroxyferulenol, (ferulenoloxo20')-13 ferulenol, and other derivatives identified

in the genuina variety of Morocco. 4-hydroxycoumarins were also identified in the *Ferula communis* in Italy.

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